

PRODUCTION OF THE JOSHI EFFECT IN OXYGEN UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE. PART VIII. INFLUENCE OF 'AGEING' UNDER FULL- AND SEMI-OZONISER EXCITATION

By S. R. MOHANTY

Influence of 'ageing' under discharge at constant applied potential V on the Joshi effect Δi in oxygen has been studied under full- and semi-ozoniser excitation. No sensible time-variation of Δi is observed in an ozoniser which had been in continuous use for twelve months. In a freshly prepared Siemens' tube, however, Δi increases progressively to a constant maximum. The possible contribution to this 'ageing' effect of changes in ionic mobility, due to cluster formation etc., is considered to be negligible. The progressive development of Δi during 'ageing' follows the equation for 'first order' reactions. Chemisorption, involving electron transference or/and sharing, is responsible for the formation of the excited boundary layer postulated by Joshi as the chief seat of the phenomenon. The continued increase in Δi to a stationary maximum is attributed to diminution, with time, of the 'work function' characteristic of the excited layer formed under discharge. Since a semi-ozoniser has a small surface exposed to the gas, the effect of 'ageing' on such a tube is small. Current changes during 'ageing' arise from variations in the electro-static capacity of the systems as a consequence of the chemisorption of oxygen on the electrode walls.

Earlier results reported the marked influence of 'ageing', i.e., a time-variation at a constant applied potential V of the conductivity i , on the magnitude of the Joshi effect, net Δi and relative % Δi , in excited chlorine (Deo, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, **A21**, 76; Goyal, *this Journal*, 1947, **24**, 201; Mallikarjunappa, *ibid.*, 1948, **25**, 197; Ramana-murthi, *ibid.*, 1948, **25**, 255), bromine (Deshmukh and Sirsikar, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci.*, 1948, **14**, 157) and iodine (Deshmukh, *this Journal*, 1949, **26**, 179). The preliminary observations of the author and Kamath (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1947, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 15) had shown that Δi in oxygen in a freshly prepared ozoniser increases with the 'age' (i. e. use) of the ozoniser. It was of interest therefore to study in some detail the time-development of Δi in oxygen under full- and semi-ozoniser excitation at constant V .

EXPERIMENTAL

The general experimental arrangement and the mode of observing Δi were essentially similar to those described in Part I (Mohanty and Kamath, *this Journal*, 1948, **25**, 405). Five typical series of observations with ozonisers A, B, B₁ and C, and a semi-ozoniser W are given in Tables I and II. The semi-ozoniser had a platinum wire as the central H. T. electrode. Ozoniser C had the following dimensions:

External diameter of the outer tube	...	20 mm.
Internal " " "	...	18
Thickness of the glass wall	...	1
External diameter of the inner tube	...	15
Internal " " "	...	13
Inter-electrode distance	...	1
Length of the electrode space	...	30.5 cm

TABLE I

Influence of 'ageing' on the Joshi effect in oxygen under full- and semi-ozoniser excitation.

Time	Ozoniser A.				Ozoniser B ₁ .				Ozoniser C.				Semi-ozoniser W.			
	<i>i_D</i>	<i>i_L</i>	Δi	% Δi	<i>i_D</i>	<i>i_L</i>	Δi	% Δi	<i>i_D</i>	<i>i_L</i>	Δi	% Δi	<i>i</i>	<i>i_L</i>	Δi	% Δi
0	7.68	6.16	1.52	19.8	8.66	7.28	1.38	15.9	7.35	6.71	0.64	8.7	7.94	7.07	0.87	11
2	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	6.78	6.00	0.78	11.5	...	...	...	...
4	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	6.48	5.57	0.91	14.0	...	...	...	...
5	...	...	...	...	7.81	6.25	1.56	20	...	...	...	...	7.62	6.93	0.69	9.1
6	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	6.25	5.29	0.96	15.4	...	...	...	...
8	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	6.16	5.2	0.96	15.6	...	...	...	...
10	...	...	...	...	7.81	6.25	1.56	20	6.16	5.1	1.06	17.2	7.62	6.82	0.80	10.5
15	...	...	...	...	7.81	6.04	1.77	22.7	...	...	...	...	7.55	6.82	0.73	9.7
20	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	6.16	4.9	1.26	20.5	...	...	...	...
25	7.68	6.25	1.43	18.6	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
30	...	...	...	...	7.75	5.92	1.83	23.6	6.16	4.58	1.58	25.7	8.43	7.48	0.95	11.3
50	7.55	6.08	1.47	19.5	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
60	...	...	...	...	7.75	5.83	1.92	24.8	6.16	4.47	1.69	27.4	8.78	7.81	0.97	11.1
75	7.55	6.08	1.47	19.5	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
90	...	...	...	...	7.75	5.83	1.92	24.8	6.08	4.24	1.84	30.3	9.17	8.06	1.11	12.1
100	7.35	5.96	1.39	18.9	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
120	...	...	...	...	7.81	5.83	1.98	25.6	6.08	4.24	1.84	30.3	9.22	8.06	1.16	12.6
125	7.48	6.00	1.48	19.8	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
150	7.35	5.79	1.56	21.2	...	...	...	...	6.08	4.12	1.96	32.2	9.33	8.06	1.27	13.6
175	7.35	5.83	1.52	20.7	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
180	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	6.08	4.12	1.96	32.2	9.38	8.06	1.32	14.1
210	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	6.08	4.12	1.96	32.2	9.49	8.19	1.30	13.7
240	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	6.08	4.12	1.96	32.2	9.54	8.19	1.35	14.2
270	...	...	...	...	8.00	5.92	2.08	26.0	6.08	4.12	1.96	32.2	9.38	8.06	1.32	14.1
300	...	...	...	...	8.06	5.92	2.14	26.6	6.08	4.12	1.95	32.2	9.49	8.06	1.43	15.1

Ozoniser A was in continuous use for about 12 months.

" B₁ " " " " over a period of 4 months, but later had been set aside for about 6 months.

" C and semi-ozoniser W were freshly prepared.

TABLE II
Influence of 'ageing' on the Joshi effect in oxygen.

Ozoniser B.*

$p_{O_2} = 456$ mm. (30°). Temp. = 28.30°. 'Ageing' potential = 10.66 kV (r. m. s.). 50Ω.

Detector = Diode 6H6 (RCA) ; half wave Inductive coupling. Source of radiations = Two 200 volt, 200 (glass) bulbs, watt 15 cm. from B.

V.	Experiment Number.									
	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	
2.67	i_B	6	3	4	2	3	3	—	—	3
	i_L	6	3	4	2	2.5	3	—	—	3
	Δi	—	—	—	—	0.5	—	—	—	—
	% Δi	—	—	—	—	16.7	—	—	—	—
2.93	i_B	8	6	7	5	6	6	6	1.5	7
	i_L	8	5	6	4	5	5	4.5	1	5
	Δi	—	1	1	1	1	1	1.5	0.5	2
	% Δi	—	16.7	14.3	20.0	16.7	16.7	25.0	33.3	28.6
3.2	i_B	9	13	10	10	13	13	13	6	15
	i_L	8.5	10	8	7	10.5	9	10	3	10
	Δi	0.5	3	2	3	2.5	4	3	3	5
	% Δi	5.6	23.1	20.0	30.0	19.2	30.8	23.1	50.0	33.3
3.47	i_B	23	26	17	18	21	23	22	16	35
	i_L	19	18	13	12	17	16	15	8	19
	Δi	4	8	4	6	4	7	7	8	16
	% Δi	17.4	30.8	23.5	33.3	19.1	30.4	31.8	50.0	45.7
3.73	i_B	89	73	35	38	40	63	67	62	91
	i_L	67	51	24	27	29	34	42	31	51
	Δi	22	22	11	11	11	29	25	31	40
	% Δi	24.7	30.1	31.4	29	27.5	46.0	37.3	50.0	44
4	i_B	128	107	76	80	76	101	112	98	120
	i_L	96	78	49	50	51	70	69	52	73
	Δi	32	29	27	30	25	31	43	46	47
	% Δi	25.0	27.1	35.6	37.5	32.9	30.7	38.4	47	39.3
4.8	i_B	197	161	137	140	140	169	174	158	186
	i_L	159	121	97	98	105	126	119	96	121
	Δi	38	40	40	42	35	43	55	62	65
	% Δi	19.3	24.9	29.2	34.4	25.0	25.5	31.6	39.2	34.9
5.33	i_B	238	192	175	178	185	183	215	190	218
	i_L	197	147	130	127	141	130	150	118	150
	Δi	41	45	45	51	44	53	65	72	68
	% Δi	17.2	23.4	25.7	28.7	23.8	29	30.2	37.9	31.2
6.93	i_B	329	269	257	263	272	306	300	269	300
	i_L	288	219	203	203	216	238	224	189	221
	Δi	41	50	54	60	56	68	76	80	79
	% Δi	12.5	18.6	21.0	22.8	20.6	22.2	25.3	29.8	26.3
8	i_B	378	311	301	305	318	356	335	313	348
	i_L	338	258	244	237	258	286	257	228	266
	Δi	40	53	57	68	60	70	78	85	82
	% Δi	10.6	17.0	19	22.3	18.9	19.2	23.3	27.2	23.6
9.6	i_B		668	357	362	378	418	393	373	406
	i_L		317	298	293	315	344	311	287	323
	Δi		51	59	69	63	74	82	86	83
	% Δi		13.9	16.5	19.1	16.7	17.7	20.9	23.1	20.5
10.7	i_B		397	383	393	422	457	432	408	442
	i_L		346	323	325	353	381	339	322	356
	Δi		51	60	68	69	76	93	86	86
	% Δi		12.8	15.7	17.3	16.4	16.6	21.5	21.1	19.5

*Freshly prepared.

TABLE III
Kinetics of the development of the Joshi effect in oxygen.
 (Ozoniser C*)

Time (t)	$\alpha = 1.32$			$\alpha' = 23.5$		
	Δi	$\alpha - \alpha'$	$k \times 10^3$, (1 st. order)	% Δi	$\alpha' - \alpha$	$k' \times 10^3$, (1 st. order)
0 min.	0.64	—	—	8.7	—	—
10	1.06	0.90	3.8	16.6	15.6	4.1
20	1.265	0.695	3.2	20.5	11.7	3.5
30	1.415	0.545	2.9	22.8	9.4	3.1
40	1.53	0.43	2.8	24.7	7.5	2.9
50	1.615	0.345	2.7	26.1	6.1	2.7
60	1.685	0.275	2.6	27.4	4.8	2.6
70	1.74	0.22	2.6	28.5	3.7	2.6
80	1.785	0.175	2.5	29.3	2.9	2.6
90	1.82	0.14	2.5	30.0	2.2	2.6
100	1.85	0.11	2.5	30.6	1.6	2.7
110	1.873	0.087	2.5	31.1	1.1	2.8
120	1.89	0.07	2.4	31.4	0.8	2.8
130	1.907	0.053	2.5	31.6	0.6	2.8
140	1.92	0.04	2.5	31.8	0.4	2.9
150	1.93 (1.96)	0.03	2.5	31.9 (32.2)	0.3	2.9

*Freshly prepared.

Ozoniser A sealed with purified oxygen at 27 mm. Hg pressure (20°) had been in use for work on the Δi phenomenon over a period of about 12 months. The discharge current i was measured with a sensitive reflection galvanometer actuated by a Cambridge vacuo-junction. At a constant applied $V = 0.93$ kV (r.m.s.) of 50 cycles frequency, i was observed at intervals of 25 minutes in dark (i_0), and when irradiated (i_t) perpendicular to the axis of the ozoniser by a battery of 200 watt incandescent (glass) bulbs run at 200 volts. From these data the corresponding values of Δi and % Δi were calculated (Table I). The next series of experiments (Table I) refers to ozoniser B (*vide supra*) sealed with purified oxygen at 331 mm. pressure (32°). This ozoniser (now designated B₁) which was in use for about 4 months for work on Δi had been set aside over a period of half year. The ozoniser was excited at 2.8 kV; i_0 and i_t were observed at intervals of 5 to 30 minutes. Similar observations (Table I) were made with a freshly prepared ozoniser C containing 52 mm. (20°) of pure oxygen subjected to discharge at 1.33 kV, and with a freshly prepared semi-ozoniser W, filled with oxygen at 250 mm. (20°) pressure and excited at 2 kV.

In another set of observations (Table II), a freshly prepared ozoniser B filled with 456 mm. (30°) of oxygen was used. Every 24 hours, the gas was subjected to continuous discharge at 10.7 kV for 1 hour (in the case of experiments 1-6, Table II) or 2 hours (in the case of experiments 7-9, Table II), and i_0 and i_t observed with the galvanometer actuated by an inductively fed diode 6H6 (RCA), used as a half-wave detector, at different V , decreased progressively.

D I S C U S S I O N .

It is seen from observations with ozoniser A (Table I) that exposure of the gas to discharge at a constant applied V for about 3 hours brings about but a small decrease in i_b (Fig. 1) and i_c . The net effect Δi , and % Δi , however, remain practically

FIG. 1

constant. Since the the ozoniser had been in use for a very considerable period, the absence of any appreciable time-variation of Δi might be ascribed to its having been already 'aged'. This deduction is supported by the results of observations on the freshly prepared ozonisers B and C, and the freshly prepared semi-ozoniser W.

From Table II, which embodies results of 9 experiments with the freshly prepared ozoniser B, it is seen that Δi as well as % Δi increase with 'age' (i.e. use) of the ozoniser. Thus, e. g., Δi at 4 kV, at the end of one hour's exposure to discharge at 10.7 kV, was 32; it increased to 47 at the same V as a result of 12 hours' exposure to discharge. The corresponding % Δi increased from 25.0 to 39.2.

i_b and i_c for the freshly prepared ozoniser C, excited at 1.33 kV, diminish with time, at first rapidly and then slowly, tending towards a constant minimum after a certain 'ageing'. On the other hand, both Δi and % Δi increase with the duration of exposure to discharge, at first rapidly and then slowly, to a constant maximum. Thus, i_b at the time of initiation of the discharge was 7.35 and decreased to 6.48 at the end of 4 minutes of exposure to discharge. On continuation of the discharge, it reduced only to 6.08 at the end of 90 minutes, remaining stationary afterwards. Similarly, i_c at the time of

initiation of the discharge was 6.71, reduced to 5.57 at the end of 4 minutes, and 4.12 at the end of 150 minutes, after which it remained constant. It is seen from above that i_c decreases over a wider interval of time than i_b . The effect Δi increased from 0.64 at the time of initiation of the discharge to 1.96 at the end of 150 minutes, after which it did not vary with the duration of exposure to discharge. The corresponding $\% \Delta i$ increased from 8.7 to 32.2, *i.e.*, by 3.7 times. As against this, it will be seen (Table I, Fig. 1) that in the case of ozoniser B, which was in use for work on Δi in oxygen for about 4 months but had been set aside for about 6 months, effect of 'ageing' is small. Thus, *e.g.*, Δi increased from 1.38 to 2.14, and $\% \Delta i$ from 15.9 to 26.6 (by 1.7 times) due to 300 minutes of continuous exposure to discharge. Both i_b and i_c decrease from respectively 8.66 and 7.28 at the time of initiation of the discharge to 7.75 and 5.83 at 90 minutes; later a small increase to 8.06 and 5.92 at 300 minutes was exhibited.

Results with the semi-ozoniser W (Table I, Fig. 1) are interesting. This has a small surface-area compared with ozonisers of the Siemens' type. It is seen that at first there is a small fall, with time, in both i_b and i_c up to 15 minutes; after this both these quantities increase tending, in each case, towards a constant maximum after prolonged exposure to discharge. Both Δi and $\% \Delta i$, on the other hand, increase progressively. The increase, however, is small compared with the results for Siemens' tubes, indicating that the influence of 'ageing' on Δi in oxygen under semi-ozoniser excitation is comparatively small. Thus, Δi increased from 0.87 at the time of initiation of the discharge to but 1.33 at the end of 5 hours of continuous exposure to discharge at 2kV. The corresponding $\% \Delta i$ increased from 11 to only 15.1.

The time-variations in electrical quantities in gaseous systems have been emphasized by Joshi (*Curr. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 548; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 25, 121) as significant for an analysis of the corresponding discharge reaction. Such variation in conductivity under constant electrical conditions in gaseous mixtures and in compound gases has been attributed to the progress of a chemical change in the system; no such simple mechanism, however, can be postulated, in the first instance, in the case of elementary gases. In the case of oxygen, exposed to discharge under conditions of the present work, the formation of ozone is found to be small (Mohanty, *this Journal*, 1949, 28, 291) and cannot therefore account for the marked variations in the current observed.

It was observed by Erikson (*Phys. Rev.*, 1921, 17, 400; 1921, 18, 100; 1922, 19, 275; 1922, 20, 117; 1924, 23, 110; 1924, 24, 502; 1929, 33, 403; 1929, 34, 635) that whereas negative ions in air showed but one mobility, the mobility of the positive ions varied with time. This result was verified by Wahlin (*ibid.*, 1922, 20, 267), and by Tyndall and Grindley (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1926, A, 110, 358). Erikson (*loc. cit.*) explains his result by assuming that ionisation involves merely the detachment of an electron from a molecule, leaving a positive monomolecular ion which soon attaches to a neutral molecule forming the final, somewhat unstable, bimolecular positive ion, while the electron almost immediately joins a neutral molecule forming a stable, negative monomolecular ion. Further, both Erikson (*loc. cit.*) and Loeb (*Phys. Rev.*, 1931, 38, 549) were of opinion that the ion was a complex of relatively few molecules, two or three at best, and that much of the reduction in mobility was due to the attractive forces between

molecules and ions not resulting in cluster formation. According to Zeleny (*ibid.*, 1929, 34, 310) ions in moist air 'are clusters which change in size under the influence of molecular bombardment, the life of each stage being sufficiently long.' Schilling (*Ann. Physik*, 1927, 8, 23) showed that 'ageing' of ions did not occur in pure air or in air saturated with water vapour.

Apart from changes in mobility due to cluster formation, discussed above, similar changes in very short time-intervals can also be brought about by charge transfer, when the ionisation potential E_i of one constituent of the gas is lower than E_i for the ionised atom or molecule (Mitchell and Ridler, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, A, 146, 911).

Since the discovery of 'ageing' of ions in air by Erikson, similar effects have been observed by Tyndall and Grindley (*ibid.*, 1926, A, 110, 314; Tyndall, Grindley and Sheppard, *ibid.*, 1928, A, 121, 172), by Bradbury (*Phys. Rev.*, 1932, 40, 508, 524) in several gases, by Loeb (*loc. cit.*), and by Tyndall and Poweill (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, A, 134, 125; 1932, A, 136, 145; Tyndall, 'Mobility of Positive Ions in Gases', Camb. Physical Tracts, Camb. Univ. Press, 1938; Powell and Brata, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1932, A, 138, 129) in other gases. Analogous but more complex effects have also been observed by Zeleny (*loc. cit.*, *Phys. Rev.*, 1930, 36, 35; 1930, 35, 1441; 1931, 38, 2239), Hamshere (*Proc. Camb. Phil. Soc.*, 1929, 25, 205; *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1930, A, 127, 298), Bradbury (*loc. cit.*), Fontell (*Soc. Sci. Fenn. Comm. Phys. Math.*, 1932, 6, 6; 1931, 5, No. 23; 1932, 6, 17), Varney (*Phys. Rev.*, 1932, 42, 547), and Luhr (*ibid.*, 1931, 38, 1730; 1933, 44, 459) on ions of greater ages in air.

A review of the vast data on ionic mobility shows that impurities, such as the residual vapours of the vacuum lubricants etc., present in minute traces (the elimination of which is beyond the usual chemical techniques) influence the mobility values to an appreciable extent (Loeb, "Electrical Discharge in Gases", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1939). This is brought about by the impurity molecules (or atoms) attaching themselves to the ions forming clusters, or by the principle of electron capture (Mitchell and Ridler, *loc. cit.*, Kallmann and Rosen, *Z. Physik*, 1930, 61, 61; Tyndall and Powell, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1930, A, 129, 162). Loeb (*op. cit.*) is of opinion that 'all the transformations observed so far in pure gases in times of the order of 10^{-2} second or less are due to the addition of a single molecule of some active impurity'.

The period, of an order of a fraction of a second, over which loss of mobility occurs in the above experiments, is of a different order of magnitude compared with that in the present work. Change in ionic mobility cannot therefore be fundamental to the marked variation, over an extended period, in i under silent discharge at constant V.

It has been observed by Bangham and Burt (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1924, A, 105, 481) that the time-variation of adsorption of a number of gases, e.g., NH_3 , N_2O , C_2H_2 , SO_2 , on glass wool follows the relationship,

$$S^m = \alpha t,$$

where S is the amount adsorbed up to the time t after admission of the gas, and m and α are constants. In view of the dependence of Δi on the formation of an adsorption-like layer on the walls of the discharge vessel (*vide infra*), it was of interest to investigate the existence or otherwise of a similar relationship, viz.,

between Δi and t . On taking logarithms, the above equation becomes

$$m \log \Delta i = \log \alpha + \log t,$$

so that, if the equation were applicable, the plots of $\log \Delta i$ (or $\log \% \Delta i$) against $\log t$ should lie on a straight line. It is evident from Fig. 2, however, that $\log \Delta i$ — $\log t$ and $\log \% \Delta i$ — $\log t$ graphs are strongly curved, except in the initial stages, corresponding to the first few minutes, where the departure from straight lines is not considerable.

FIG. 2

Equilibrium in cases of sorption on plane surfaces is attained within a very short period after introduction of the gas. Thus, *e.g.*, Bawn (cf. S. J. Gregg, "The Adsorption of Gases by Solids", Methuen & Co. Ltd., London, 1934, p. 18) working on adsorption of a number of gases on mica found that equilibrium was complete in three minutes at the very most. The freshly prepared discharge tubes, after having been filled with oxygen and sealed off, were set aside, prior to excitation, for about 10 hours. During this interval the film of oxygen on the electrode walls due to physical adsorption would have been completely formed.

The theory of the effect Δi as advanced by Joshi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1946, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 26; 1947, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 25; *Curr. Sci.*, 1946, 15, 281; 1947, 16, 19) contemplates three stages: (i) formation on the container walls of a boundary layer derived, in part, from adsorption of ions and excited molecules under the applied field, when intense enough to breakdown the gas dielectrically (above the 'threshold potential' V_m); (ii) electron emission from this electrode layer under external irradiation; and (iii) capture of these photo-electrons by the electronegative elements in the discharge space to form slow moving negative ions which reduce i by a space charge effect. Stage (i) is fundamental not only to the Joshi effect but a number of other phenomena, *e.g.*, 'ageing', and the newly observed periodic effect in N_2O-H_2 (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, *Chem. Sec.*, p. 51; Joshi and

Deshmukh, *Nature*, 1945, 155, 483) and S-N₂ (Deshmukh and Sirsikar, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, A28, 175) interaction under electrical discharge. Evidence in support of the electrode layer postulate is afforded by the observed marked influence of the nature of the wall material (Cherian, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1945, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 17) on the magnitude of Δi , and of the influence of sorbed chlorine (Rao, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, A27, 72) on Δi in air. Stages (ii) and (iii) are instantaneous and fully reversible. It follows therefore that a time-variation in Δi under 'ageing' is determined practically entirely by the extent to which stage (i) occurs. Hence, the curves Δi (or % Δi)-time represent the course of the reaction occurring in (i). The difference in the final stationary value for Δi (or % Δi) and the value at the commencement Δi_0 (or % Δi_0) measures the total net production of the change, and corresponds to the initial concentration term a in the familiar equations for the (chemical) reaction velocities. Likewise, the difference in Δi , (or % Δi) at any time t and Δi_0 (or % Δi_0) is a measure of x , the amount changed. Results in Table III show that the values of Δi (or % Δi), reckoned since the commencement of 'ageing' under discharge for ozoniser C yield a sensibly constant value for the velocity coefficient k , when the equation for first order reactions is used. Values for Δi (or % Δi) used in the calculation of k were read off from the corresponding smooth curves in Fig. 1. The above constancy in k also applicable to results (not shown) obtained with freshly prepared ozonisers other than C, which were excited at different V. Ramanamurthi (*loc. cit.*) has shown that the progressive development of Δi during 'ageing' under discharge in freshly prepared Siemens' tubes filled with chlorine as well follows the equation for the first order reactions.

As required for a reaction of the first order, the plots of $\log (a-x)$ [or $\log (a'-x')$] against t lie on a straight line (Fig. 3.). The values for k and k' , calculated from the slopes of the corresponding straight lines, are respectively 0.0229 and 0.0235. It is of interest that k and k' are, within the limits of experimental error, the same.

That the progress of Δi under 'ageing' follows the unimolecular law for chemical reactions suggests that the type of adsorption involved in the formation of the boundary layer postulated by Joshi may be predominantly chemisorption, as discriminated from physical adsorption. This last, attributed by Langmuir to the operation of van der Waals' forces, occurs practically instantaneously (*vide supra*), and cannot therefore lead to the time-development of Δi . Chemisorption, on the other hand, associated with molecules possessing high activation energy (and therefore particularly probable under discharge), formed with the aid of valency forces and characterised by a large heat of adsorption, would appear to be fundamental for the formation of the boundary layer. This excited gas-layer on the electrode walls therefore is a consequence of the molecules on the surface being activated due to ionic bombardment under discharge at a constant applied V and as a result undergoing a more stable condensation on the walls by means of electron transference or/and sharing.

Photo-electric emission from the boundary potential layer is governed by a 'work function' smaller than the corresponding ionisation potential in the gaseous condition. Occurrence of Δi at frequencies too small for photo-ionisation therefore follows (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 19). With continuous activation due to ionic bombardment under discharge (as obtains during 'ageing'), the 'work function' should diminish and

FIG. 3

Δi increase correspondingly to a stationary maximum, as observed.

A semi-ozoniser has a small surface exposed to the gas. Adsorption, and therefore time-variation of Δi in such a system is small, as observed.

Grateful thanks of the author are due to Professor S. S. Joshi for having suggested the problem, for his keen interest and valuable advice. The author is also thankful to Mr. G. S. Kamath for his kind help in a part of the work.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY, BANARAS.

Received April 11, 1950.